

FOSSR

FOSTERING OPEN SCIENCE IN SOCIAL SCIENCE RESEARCH

DELIVERABLE 9.1 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

Deliverable leaders: Emanuela Reale, Serena Fabrizio
(CNR-IRCrES)

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<i>Abstract</i>	The document contains the dissemination plan of the FOSSR project with the main communication objectives, dissemination actions and events, activity planning and main impact indicators.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The background mission of the FOSSR project relies on creating and strengthening awareness and knowledge of data and methodologies used in empirical social sciences among a wide audience, through maintaining and reinforcing of relevant Research Infrastructures (RI), while fostering the development of a research and social environment conducive to an open, shared and simplified data access via innovative interfaces. The project will concretely contribute to the effective implementation of the ‘open science’ for social science researchers by providing innovative tools and services for research, shared virtual environment for data access and a wide and varied package of training courses, sessions and programmes (FOSSR DoW, 2022).

FOSSR adopts the common theme of the development of Open Science in the Italian context with the goal of creating a framework of tools and services for the social science scholar community involving the RIs in social sciences coordinated by CNR, namely CESSDA, SHARE and RISIS. The framework should take the form of an integrated knowledge sharing platform, a single point of access to all the tools and services made available by the Italian nodes of social science infrastructures.

FOSSR fosters the building of an Italian Open Science Cloud, along the lines of the European Open Science Cloud project, in which to integrate innovative services developed by the project for data collection, data curation and fairness and data analysis on economic and societal change.

FOSSR wants to promote toward multiple audiences, a widespread knowledge and awareness of the data and methodologies employed in empirical social science, fostering the growth of a broad societal environment favorable to further thriving of social science research in Italy, providing easy, open, streamlined access to social science data through innovative interfaces

1.1 FOSSR Objectives and Ambition

FOSSR has the general aim of promoting, towards multiple audiences, a widespread knowledge and awareness of the data and methodologies employed in empirical social science, by providing (i) systematic and organized knowledge (also through summary harmonized data) about available social science data resources in Italian data archives, especially the CESSDA Archive, already object of the grand infrastructural proposal; (ii) resources supporting methodological advancement as to data collection and data analysis, especially important for RISIS to understand the design, the implementation, and the outcome of research and innovation policies, which can improve the robustness of empirical evidence produced for policy makers and to deal with new research questions, and (iii) tools and services to make publicly available advanced probability panels for longitudinal analyses to support important survey such as SHARE, complementing them with a network of online laboratories. The integration of this pool of resources shall concretely contribute to the realization of open science for scholars in social sciences, going with an important program of scientific training for the production and analysis of social science based on FAIR empirical data.

One further key objective is setting a new generation of young researchers in social sciences, by hiring several researchers and technologists with fixed time contracts, which will become highly skilled human resources in data science and data management in social science research,

and by funding 20 PhD positions to train early career researchers in the field.

FOSSR is also aimed at fostering the growth of a broad societal environment favorable to further thriving of social science research in Italy, providing easy, open, streamlined access to social science data through innovative interfaces (data exploration portals, time series, interactive visualizations), and through online data analysis software aimed at students, along with divulgation resources about social science methodology. These aspects are particularly aimed at civil society organizations (NGOs, etc.), students, ordinary citizens, to foster a widespread societal awareness of social science data, results, methods to promote an easier and more user-friendly dissemination.

The main investment shall be on the creation of a suitable IT infrastructure and a network of data center to provide researchers access online and onsite, and to support the workflow of the proposed collaborative projects. One of the subsequent goals of FOSSR will be to develop innovative tools and services for data collection and data analyses, and to support participating users in the acquisition and use of advanced equipment and software for social science research needed for collaborative studies and projects. The achievement of the above-mentioned goals can be reached by means of an online platform – the Open Cloud, acting also as a dissemination layer, intermediating between data producers, archives, and the broader shop floor of users (both scholars and stakeholders), assuring access intermediating between data producers, archives, and the broader shop floor of users (both scholars and stakeholders), assuring access also to multiple software interfaces, geared at different audiences, methodological content, and training materials.

1.2 Purpose and scope of this document

The present deliverable introduces the planning of dissemination and communication activities envisioned in the context of the **Work Package 9 (WP9) “Communication, dissemination and outreach”** of the FOSSR project and demonstrates the achievement of the 1-2 milestones associated with the WP (see CHAPTERS 4-5).

The deliverable describes objectives and actions to foster results, tools, and services developed by the thematic network of infrastructures composed by CESSDA ERIC, SHARE ERIC, and RISIS with the aim at promoting proactive communication, pushing dissemination on contents and opportunities, raising awareness on their innovative potential, encouraging the exchange of ideas and participation.

2. PRIORITIES

Social sciences are a broad and a highly fragmented field in terms of data availability, ownership, and usage because of:

- a) the importance of commercial data and distributed datasets developed by researchers or research organizations with their resources, at limited scale, and with specific objectives,
- b) the limited accumulation of harmonization efforts.

However, research in social sciences has an important value to provide vital information for the so-called evidence-based policy, thus the possibility to ground policy design and policy implementation and assessment on robust scientific evidence about the effects, and outcome of public policies, about ideas, values, attitudes, perceptions, and psychological aspects driving human behaviour.

There is a clear need for creating a linkage between the existing infrastructures in social sciences, which would allow connecting diverse communities of scholars by supplying a common platform of data sources and innovative services and resources, fostering interoperability, bringing users to data and their methods (enabling access), and a single access point where researchers can find data available for their investigations.

2.1 Main themes and actions

Communication and dissemination actions will be devoted to foster results, tools, and services developed by the thematic network of infrastructures composed by CESSDA ERIC, SHARE ERIC, and RISIS. The objectives are promoting proactive communication, pushing dissemination on contents and opportunities, raising awareness on their innovative potential, encouraging the exchange of ideas and participation.

Communication actions will be performed through a variety of channels, including a dedicated website, the CNR Outreach platform, and social media.

Dissemination actions will target specific groups – especially those located in the South of Italy with a special attention to the promotion of gender equality – to improve their understanding about what FOSSR can offer.

Linked to FOSSR main objectives a priority will be the development of a gateway for the promotion of Open Science practices and the discovery of existing resources for research on economic and social change. Furthermore, networking activities will be promoted with the aim of structuring the collaboration with other thematic networks of research infrastructures in the area of Social and Cultural Innovation.

2.2 SWOT analysis

This part highlights opportunities and possible shortcomings for the FOSSR development also related to the risk analysis presented in the DOW. To this aim we propose a SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats analysis), which might be helpful to individuate and analyse internal and external issues that could have an impact on the sustainability of the project.

The graph below problematized the main key-factors related to priorities and actions associated to FOSSR achievements under the SWOT scheme.

Strengths

Existing communities of the RIs. CESSDA ERIC, SHARE ERIC and RISIS provide services and curated data along the FAIR principles to a vast number of scholars as it is demonstrated by the access requests for research purposes, and by the impact produced in terms of new projects and publications. The mentioned RIs are also important for non-academic users such as stakeholders and policy makers.

Past experiences in training and PhD courses. Almost all partners involved in the project have decades of experience in planning and organizing training especially related to the exploitation of IRs. Many PhD students have been involved in courses over the years and more than one thesis has been followed on topics and development of methodologies related to the project. In particular, FOSSR has the ambition to directly fund dedicated PhD fellowships and a master's program.

Competences of the partners involved. The CNR Institutes involved have robust competences in the activities connected to the RIs involved in the project, as to advanced methods for data collection, data curation and fairness, integration of data from different sources, advanced methods for statistical analysis and capabilities to train scholars through different tools, both online and onsite. Furthermore, the institutes involved in FOSSR have relevant expertise in dissemination and communication of outputs and outcome realized within an IR project, which are crucial mean to increase the possibility of the project to get a social impact.

Weaknesses

Integration tools. The main investment shall be the creation of a suitable IT infrastructure and a network of data center to provide researchers access online and onsite, and to support the

workflow of the proposed collaborative projects. The integration of resources shall also contribute to improve the coverage and to broaden the audience of the RIs involved, increasing opportunities of cross fertilization and interdisciplinary research initiatives.

Effective use of resources. Different researchers have specific needs that FOSSR tools and services can meet. Researchers play an important role in the circulation of results and tailoring to the policy issues of the stakeholders that employ them. This is an important audience to be engaged deeply in the FOSSR tools' exploitation.

Networking (internal and external)

Internal. It is crucial to sustain visibility and achievement of FOSSR resources. FOSSR partners have to be aware about the need of a circularity in the exchange on information and output from WPs activities. The development of a workspace dedicated to the sharing of internal documents and inputs could be useful to overcome this current weakness.

External. The first challenge is strengthening the linkages between FOSSR and the other thematic networks of research infrastructures in the area of Social and Cultural Innovation (H2IOSC, RESILIENCE.ITA). The second is related to the integration as far as possible of the FOSSR initiative with universities that are Italian nodes of infrastructures thematically linked to FOSSR (GSS and GUIDE).

Opportunities

Open Cloud. An online platform with the aim at acting also as a dissemination layer, intermediating between data producers, archives, and the broader shop floor of users (both scholars and stakeholders), assuring access intermediating between data producers, archives, and the broader shop floor of users (both scholars and stakeholders), assuring access also to multiple software interfaces, geared at different audiences, methodological content, and training materials.

Innovation in data collection and analysis. An entire WP is dedicated to enable FOSSR to gather machine-readable and -interoperable knowledge by automatically capturing and formalising socially, economically, and cognitively relevant schemata and models.

Longitudinal and panel data. Italy lacks a long-standing tradition of panel surveys; this project acknowledges the need to build new tools and foster existing infrastructures providing statistical information (also from administrative sources) to support the future actions of researchers, institutions, and policy makers.

Involvement of SSH scholars. The role of young researchers is central to increase the awareness of the prospective offered by the development of new interdisciplinary research areas with a high social and technological impact. They should be the focus of FOSSR efforts, encouraging the excellence in SSH research. The challenge is also to emphasize the greater openness of these research infrastructures to the scholarly communities.

Knowledge graph. The construction of such a semantic knowledge graph is crucial for the definition of a common knowledge representation layer for fostering a shared understanding, thus harmonising the knowledge soup consisting of the heterogeneous semantics associated with the data collected. The adoption of a knowledge engineering task-based and agile

methodology that requires the iterative involvement of domain experts and stakeholders for the identification of ontological commitments and their corresponding assessment.

Threats

Local barriers in South Italy. Despite the significant investment in infrastructure resources with data centers, and in high skilled human capital with the financing of PhD grants (mainly in Southern universities), the efforts to engage academics from universities in southern Italy and to attract young data scientists remain crucial.

Institutional context. The variety of stakeholders, interlocutors, and potential users from broad public sectors also presents critical issues related to collaboration possibilities, timing, and structural and organizational diversities that need to be considered in the stages and occasions of engagement.

Awareness of SSH scholars. FOSSR wants to promote a widespread knowledge and awareness of the data and methodologies employed in empirical social science, fostering the growth of a broad societal environment favourable to further thriving of social science research in Italy, providing easy, open, streamlined access to social science data through innovative interfaces. Scholars' awareness of the potential and the interest in the tools, data, and methodologies is crucial to the visibility and exploitation of the Open Cloud.

Long-term sustainability. The sustainability over time of the FOSSR project is extremely challenging. The tool that the project is supposed to realize need public resources to be maintained. However, also the internal capability of the RIs involved in the building of the common Open Cloud is important, by trying to capture external resources that could be provided by external calls for proposals, and by attracting other national funding sources.

3. AUDIENCES

All the activities developed will be targeted to the broad audiences of the RIs, composed of scholars, students, practitioners, policy makers, officers, and civil servants. WP9 develops actions to disseminate results, tools, and services, promoting open access (publications), transnational access and Fairness, with the exploitation of the Open Aire Knowledge Graph.

The communication and dissemination activities developed are directed to a broad audience, composed by:

- FOSSR partners (internal and external communication).
- Scholars in the SS field (End Users) and from other neighbouring fields (researchers and officers of relevant organizations).
- Policy makers such as government at national and local level, Statistical Offices and Statistical Units.
- Core Stakeholders (Relevant organizations, Statistical offices, Other relevant projects and

initiatives, Press and Media).

To start, a snowball approach will be used from the existing contacts collected during the preparation of the proposal, including CESSDA, SHARE and RISIS Italian communities, and during the kick off meeting. The process will target only those that will express an interest in FOSSR services and tools by accepting to be informed of the project activities.

The FOSSR Community, will be consolidated through strategic activities organized according to the various users with the aim to involve month after month a broader community. For instance, experts, researchers, representatives of Associations active in the field involved in CESSDA ERIC, SHARE ERIC and RISIS past events will be contacted and **FOSSR mailing lists and Newsletter** subscribers, will be invited to participate to FOSSR activities.

The mentioned actions will be developed using a marketing campaign tool and according to GDPR agreement rules.

3.1 FOSSR Partners

All partners are involved in external communication and dissemination activities in order to:

1. provide input for production of press releases.
2. product local leaflets, (e.g., training leaflets, learning sessions leaflets), according to NRRP-MUR¹ leaflet templates, and policy briefs.
3. organise local meetings in respect to all other activities.
4. present FOSSR with paper, posters or sessions at scientific conferences and events.

FOSSR partners have been and will be involved in the realization of interviews, to explain focuses of their FOSSR project tasks to its community.

They also must contribute by insert FOSSR results in a dedicated Zenodo community space, writing pieces for FOSSR newsletter, propose articles and news related to FOSSR on their communication outputs (e.g., organization website or social media); twitting or rewetting FOSSR content; making available their networks contact to develop a FOSSR mailing list and to spread a periodical newsletter.

Internal communication with FOSSR partners aims at improving communication among partners, with Ministry of University and Research and to provide skills to the partners to collaborate in the external communication.

3.2 End users: scholars in SS and neighbouring fields

Core FOSSR end users are scholars from SS field and from scholars from other neighbouring fields. Communication team will build an end-user mailing list, also in this case starting from existing contacts and engaging with researchers and analysts within stakeholder organizations, because they are often critical to the development of productive interactions between the

¹ <https://www.mur.gov.it/pnrr/strumenti-di-attuazione/Linee-Guida-Soggetti-Attuatori/informazione-e-comunicazione>.

academic community and stakeholders.

Three interaction modes have been selected: sharing contacts with training participants, engaging users in programming events, and developing participative events (see Par. 5) targeted to different users.

CESSDA ERIC, SHARE ERIC and RISIS users will be reach initially, but the mailing list will be enlarged with other potential users, coming from training activities, dissemination, and communication events.

3.3 Policy makers

FOSSR will exploit its existing contacts to policy makers starting from CESSDA ERIC, SHARE ERIC and RISIS as well as explore new opportunities to gain influence on policy areas and specific policies relevant to the project's goals. FOSSR will establish new contacts with national regional policy makers such as Ministries and Departments of Education, as well as other relevant Public Organizations potentially sensitive to the project aims. They will be engaged to jointly organize workshops and/or working sessions to present results and discuss their needs with a view of learning from these interactions about the future directions of FOSSR development.

3.4 Core stakeholders

Relevant organizations

The variety of stakeholders and of their interests drives FOSSR to develop a specific policy of targeted interactions privileging their collective associations (like other Research Organizations, Public Offices, Public Departments, NGOs, etc.).

This group of stakeholders will be enlarged globally through the development of policy briefs, online seminars, and webinars and though the extensive use of FOSSR communication instruments: the website, a widely circulated newsletter, blog, social media.

Universities and Schools

FOSSR invests in the training of a new generation of researchers using the RIs resources, opening 20 PhD positions (of which 50% in universities of the South), which allow to push the formation of a new pool of scholars in data science and the planning of one course at Master level and PhD courses at universities. This action will be developed through specific agreements with the universities where CNR has already General agreement for research cooperation signed.

The quality of the outcome and the actions toward promoting high level training and public awareness shall increase the number of PhD students and early career researchers, especially those in the South of Italy, which improve their knowledge and therefore develops different uses of the innovative methods and instruments for data collection and for data analysis

provided by FOSSR.

Users will access the online FOSSR resources under a completely open conditions for research purposes; users are also supposed to integrate the data available in the Open Cloud Platform with data and analysis developed, thus improving practices and culture about the value of the open circulation of knowledge.

Other relevant projects and infrastructures

Research infrastructures present in other fields, e.g., often benefit greatly from communicating and sharing their experiences, which can lead to important synergies. The existing and growing network of other relevant projects, initiatives and infrastructures will be exploited through an effective communication channel to attract partners outside the core FOSSR network.

A connection with them will be established using FOSSR social media (e.g., Twitter, LinkedIn). This connection will be implemented with FOSSR newsletter circulation, National level meetings, targeted Networking actions.

Press and media

Press and media are linked to the above "general public" target group and represent an important stakeholder group as they play a key role in shaping public opinion and informing the public about new initiatives in main FOSSR infrastructures topics and tools.

Press and media are also the channels through which the project communicate how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges.

To reach press and media, main instruments will be publication of FOSSR main results. Also, the most relevant meetings (e.g., the Policy sessions), could be a powerful resource to engage press and media interests. Spreading FOSSR news on social media as Twitter will help FOSSR to engage targeted journalist. Communication and team will develop a dedicated mailing list to involve directly press and media.

General public

FOSSR is also aimed at fostering the growth of a broad societal environment favourable to further thriving of social science research in Italy, providing easy, open, streamlined access to social science data through innovative interfaces (data exploration portals, time series, interactive visualizations), and through online data analysis software aimed at students, along with divulgation resources about social science methodology.

These aspects are particularly aimed at civil society organizations, ordinary citizens, to foster a widespread societal awareness of social science data, results, methods to promote an easier and more user-friendly dissemination.

Main tools to engage public remain FOSSR social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube channel). Awareness people not necessarily directly involved in the field will be raised, on the importance of open research infrastructures to develop new knowledge production.

3.5 Dissemination and engagement charts

FOSSR takes into account the broader impact of its activities and on its core community.

Communication team periodically collect viewpoints and insights of FOSSR most important stakeholders and actively address their perspectives and needs in order to improve dissemination activities, to strengthen FOSSR visibility and outputs.

Relationships with stakeholders are establishing through consultation and dialogue, with a key focus on the following stakeholder groups: FOSSR users, FOSSR partners, policy makers, core organizations etc. A detailed overview of the stakeholder groups has been developed in the first part of this plan.

The present charter outlines FOSSR approach to stakeholder engagement and sets a few principles to ensure contacts with them. It should allow to develop strong relationships with stakeholders and to enlarge the network of relationships.

By seeking stakeholders' and end users' perspectives, we are able to:

- Manage FOSSR reputation
- Establish dedicated tools that meet the community needs.
- Sharpen FOSSR research methodologies and strategies.
- Better understand the institutional context and policy framework.
- Continuously address research issues and risks.
- Identify emerging communicative opportunities and channels.
- Explore partnership opportunities.
- Seek support and establish cooperation with other networks and organizations.

In return, stakeholders and end users do also benefit from a transparent line of communication with us to:

- Understand FOSSR research strategy.
- Comprehend the context in which FOSSR operate.
- Become familiar with the FOSSR position on policies and regulations.

We use multiple platforms to engage with end users, stakeholders, and policy makers, to share FOSSR viewpoints and to gather internal/external insights. The appropriate level of engagement is based on the research objectives, the scope of the engagement and the type of stakeholders involved.

The CHART of the most important engagement activities is given below².

² The dissemination chart will be developed according to the milestone "Opening of the FOSSR social media pages (FB, Twitter, Youtube, LinkedIn)" by February 2023 (Bimester 2).

4. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIONS

Consistency, clarity, attractiveness, and timeliness are the basic characteristics of effective communication and dissemination efforts; to ensure homogeneity and coherence in the contents, all the actions developed will be possibly monitored and planned by an editorial team composed of the task leaders, a representative of WP8³ (for coordination with related activities) and the WP leader.

The editorial staff will meet initially to establish editorial and publication lines for news, posts, events, and dissemination contents and then through periodic meetings to define medium- and long-term strategies and actions.

4.1 Branding and logo

Branding concerns the promotion of a broad use of the FOSSR logo according to Ministry of Universities and Research guidelines, and rules regarding the uses of NPRR and EU logos and templates⁴ in order to ensure consistency and uniformity both in the visual identity of the project and to highlight the financial support received.

As indicated in Article 34 of Regulation (EU) 2021/241, recipients of Union funding shall

³ WP8 “Capacity building and training”

⁴ <https://www.mur.gov.it/it/pnrr/strumenti-di-attuazione/Linee-Guida-Soggetti-Attuatori/informazione-e-comunicazione>

Union funding shall make known its origin and ensure its visibility, including through the Union's logo, in accordance with the established technical characteristics, and the statement 'Funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU', in particular when promoting actions and results, by disseminating coherent, effective and proportionate information to different audiences, including the media and the general public.

Furthermore, the new CNR logo has just been released which replaces the old versions with a new CNR Visual Identity Manual⁵. Considering the institutional indications mentioned above, below we present some graphic examples of uses:

Figure 1 – Institutional logos use

Upper side

Down side

The main rules to harmonize dissemination contents and activities and to enlarge FOSSR visibility as brand are the following:

- Use of the official FOSSR logo when it's possible combined with NRRP-MUR official logos.

⁵https://www.cnr.it/sites/default/files/public/media/servizi/Manuale_Identit%C3%A0%20Visiva_Cnr_28nov2022.pdf

- Use of the official font Times New Roman (Text) and Calibri (Titles) (supported by Microsoft) for all documents and materials derived from FOSSR and NPRR.
- Use of MUR NRRP slide templates for all presentations of work derived from FOSSR.
- Use of Poster and leaflet templates provided by FOSSR communication team when Partners organize an event.
- Indication of ‘FOSSR’ before the name of the datasets and other facilities developed within the project.
- The quotation of FOSSR as source of data shared.
- The mention of FOSSR in the acknowledgment of paper published (also preliminary versions such as working papers) as follow: “This work was supported by FOSSR (Fostering Open Science in Social Science Research), funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU under NPRR Grant agreement n. MUR IR0000008”.

Dissemination and communication team will upload in the Repository template, formats and rules on branding and will manage the periodic updating of them.

4.2 Kick off meeting

The Kickoff Meeting was aimed at presenting and discussing the different actions foreseen in the FOSSR project. It took place in Rome, at the venue of the Project Coordinator CNR-IRCrES, the 25th November 2022, in hybrid format with the participation of Project Partners and main stakeholders.

The minutes of the Kick Off Meeting on the topics that have been discussed and the list of participants are reported in the KOM Report (Milestone 9.1) presented in December 2022.

All the Presentations are available in Section 4. Annexes of the KOM Report and at ZENODO Platform <https://zenodo.org/record/7458327#.Y6M1W3bMKhM>.

The videos of the presentations have been edited and uploaded on the FOSSR Youtube Channel at the following link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=I_LSsfKHr2k.

4.3 Website

The key role of the website is to communicate the activities related to the three infrastructures involved in the project: CESSDA ERIC, SHARE ERIC, and RISIS. Creating the website is also critical in raising awareness of the opportunities for the interested audience, attracting new users of services and tools, and disseminating project outputs. The website serves as a resource for understanding FOSSR and what it has to offer, how to join the community, what benefits it may provide to researchers and stakeholders, and how to access the results and open materials produced. It will keep information on the activities developed within WP3, WP4, WP5, and WP8, promotional materials, templates, videos, and outputs such as the policy brief foreseen by Task 9.4. The communication of most of the initiatives presented through the website will be managed, coordinating the effort with the existing platform "CNR Outreach".

During the first six months of the project, the website structure was established. The foreseen website's sections will be:

- a. Project – this section will describe the project and the expected objectives. Moreover, a link to the official documents will be available.
- b. Partners/Network – this section will illustrate the partner involved, the planned boards and committees, the partners, and the stakeholders.
- c. Resources - this section will contain the link to access the platforms and all the related resources (Datasets, Indicators, Methods, Services, etc.)
- d. Media – this section will contain links to all the social media related to the project. Moreover, a newsletter and/or a blog are envisaged.
- e. Events – this section will contain a list (with the associated links) of all the events, lectures, and workshops related to the project.
- f. Tools – this section will be confidential and contain useful tools for the project's partner (e.g., management, reports, etc.)

Also, CNR- UVR, in charge of the website's management, published a call for the position of technologist needed to support the content creation of the website and is proceeding with the selection of the candidate.

CNR-UVR also started the call for tenders necessary to implement the technical aspects of the website.

4.4 Press and news

Press review: press releases will be generated by FOSSR communication team in relation to publication of FOSSR main results. Press releases will be targeted at key players, (e.g. relevant national/international authority departments, national and international media) and published on the Press Release section of the website. Communication team will actively follow up the releases to assure maximum coverage. Partnerships will collaborate with selected newspapers in the partner cities to assure continuous information coverage.

NEWS: weekly announcements of news related to FOSSR development (short news for quick reading on achievements, publications, forthcoming activities, etc. and links where one can get more information).

Newsletter: a periodical (every six month) update of ongoing activities and achievements pre-announced using the News section. News will be prepared as short papers (100-200 words) with a picture/design.

4.5 Social media actions

Social media actions are crucial for raising interest and outreach on the thematic network of infrastructures and fostering participation in the activities developed within FOSSR.

A strong and well-maintained social media presence is the first mean for staying in touch with scholars, practitioners, and stakeholders in the field, particularly the younger generation.

Main actions can foresee the publication of attractive posts directed at specific content on the website and sharing videos and promoting materials.

One of main goal of communication activity will be the intensive use of Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and use of You Tube for a wide distribution of videos.

YouTube, Twitter, and Facebook will remain the most used channels to promote project updates and results, and a FOSSR profile for each of them has been created. Social media, especially Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, and YouTube, have spread across the whole society as prominent communication channels. To extend the project target audience (specially to involve the great public and not only sectorial experts) FOSSR is integrating these media tools strategically in the communication activities.

Starting from M3, according to the milestone on Social Media opening, dissemination team will share content about the project, its general view, its aims, and plans with weekly post and tweet, planning the contents in weekly meeting.

After, new contents will be created about the structure of FOSSR and its infrastructures. The reach of FOSSR posts will be implemented with photos and external links. Producing short clips on network's partners experience and putting them on a public video channel, (e.g., YouTube) serves several audiences and even offers a feedback channel for the project. Partners, events and training activities are the main reference for FOSSR events news, and for the latter case, specific graphic cards will be created for different kind of events (e.g. training, policy sessions, webinars etc.)

Relevant post of FOSSR partners and stakeholders are re-tweeted constantly, also announcing updates and direct their messages to the attention of stakeholders by use of hashtags (example #PNRR) and handles (examples: @PNRR).

4.6 Communication and dissemination products

Policy Brief

FOSSR Policy Brief Series aims at disseminating key results coming from FOSSR used as demonstrators of the FOSSR value to address social and political issues, thus, to improve its exploitation for evidence-based policy making. The outcomes should be presented through short documents, elaborated on a specific template⁶, pointing out the main policy issues at stake, demonstrating the contribution provided by FOSSR, and what new avenues for research are now open. Policy briefs could be produced by different WPs and are coordinated by WP9. They will be circulated around the broad community of scholars, stakeholders, and policy makers through the FOSSR communication channels, including the website for downloading.

Partners of FOSSR responsible for core services and data building are involved to contribute to the Series; partners involved in the FOSSR Policy Meetings shall prepare a policy brief in advance.

⁶ Templates for policy briefs and instructions on how to prepare are in the Annexes of the deliverable.

The structure of the Policy Brief should be articulated in these sections:

1. *Introduction and questions*
2. *Topic addressed*
3. *How FOSSR can address*
4. *Policy evidence*

According to the milestone “Setting of the format for Online policy makers’ sessions and Policy Briefs” (Bimester 1) in the Annex 1 is reported the graphic format of the FOSSR Policy Brief Series.

The editing will follow these mail rules⁷:

Purpose. A policy brief presents a concise summary of information that can help readers understand, and likely make decisions about, government policies. Policy briefs may give objective summaries of relevant research, suggest possible policy options, or go even further and argue for courses of action.

Target. Policy makers: busy people, and probably not specialists in your area. They are likely to read only something that looks attractive, appears interesting, and is short and easy to read.

Language. A clear language is especially important in policy briefs. If you find yourself using technicalities, try to replace it with language that is more direct: a non-specialist reader would be more likely to understand. When specialized terminology is necessary, explain it quickly and clearly to ensure that your reader does not get confused.

Reference. A policy brief might synthesize scientific findings, but it will deploy them for a very specific purpose: to help readers decide what they should do. It will relate the findings to current policy debates, with an emphasis on applying the research outcomes rather than assessing the research procedures. A “policy” reference is more desirable than a “scientific” reference.

Posters and Leaflets

Posters and leaflet are dissemination materials periodically produced by communication team to advertise about contents and development of FOSSR activities and to support the dissemination during key Conferences and other events in which FOSSR is involved.

The first batch of materials realized will be on the website in a dedicated section.

Videos and storytelling

These products are a powerful tool to disseminate FOSSR general overview, as its main objectives and development. FOSSR video production has been divided in two categories: graphic and report videos. Graphic videos are useful to explain the most technical aspects of FOSSR infrastructure, e.g., the structure and the contents of FOSSR datasets. Report videos are

⁷ Cfr. Library of policy brief of European Commission (SSH), available at: https://ec.europa.eu/research/social-sciences/index.cfm?pg=library&lib=policy_briefs; Policy brief on Research Infrastructures of Science Europe available at <https://www.scienceeurope.org/our-resources/policybrief-on-research-infrastructures-in-eu-framework-programming/>

often enriched with partner's interviews and are related to FOSSR main events.

5. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION EVENTS

5.1 Online seminars and Webinars

Six online seminars/webinars will be organized within the project duration, three of them by the 9th bimester, the other 3 by the 15th bimester.

Online seminars are targeted to a wide academic audience within and outside the FOSSR community – researchers from universities and public research centres, university students - and are intended to promote the exchange of research ideas, presenting methods and findings developed by FOSSR thematic network, building a shared knowledge background and activating a collective process of knowledge co-creation. Sharing and co-creation of knowledge promoted by the seminars will inform and nourish the techno-scientific decisions that will need to be taken within the project.

Each seminar will last 60-90 minutes, with the participation of 1 or 2 invited/selected speakers, 4-10 selected panelists and at least 2 facilitators. The indicative structure of the seminars is the following: 1 or 2 speakers working in FOSSR research field – from project partners institutions or external, depending on the relevance of their research and the use of CESSDA ERIC, SHARE ERIC and RISIS - will present contributions of no more than 20 minutes; a roundtable with FOSSR representatives will follow, lasting no more than 45 minutes; the audience will have the possibility to ask questions via chat in the last 10-15 minutes. Indeed, the seminars will be open to interested audience who will register to the events. One of the privileged targets for the seminars is represented by PhD students and early researchers, but also university students are welcome, mainly those attending Social and Political Sciences, Economy and Statistics faculties.

As for the contents of the online seminars, possible proposals of topics to be addressed are: i) already existing research infrastructures, with special attention to those involved in FOSSR; ii) theoretical models underlying the main international social surveys and their possible evolution; iii) building FOSSR panel and main research questions; iv) FOSSR virtual panels.

The selected speakers, invited by the WP9 organizers in agreement with FOSSR coordinator, will have to share in advance with the panel an extended abstract of their contribution including the scientific references, in order to nourish the debate. These abstracts and reports of the seminar contents will be made available on the project website, nourishing a common repository of dissemination materials.

Online webinars are targeted to a larger audience, including not only the scientific community working in universities and public research centres and university students, but also researchers working in the private sector, practitioners, and various kinds of social actors/stakeholders - e. g. policy makers, officers, administrative staff, associations, companies. The webinars are intended to give visibility to the project and discuss specific tools and services developed within FOSSR to investigate economic and societal change, in order to increase the awareness about their public availability and collect inputs and feedback from the civil society in order to foster their usability in different contexts. The events represent a co-working space and open

innovation environment in which the various actors collaborate, share knowledge and co-create new ideas. This can make it possible to intercept three principles connected to the European Responsible Research and Innovation approach: 1) the activation of an inclusive dialogic process among all the social actors involved; 2) the alignment of research processes and products to the needs, values, and expectations of society; 3) the co-creation of innovation and research results from which everyone benefits.

The format of the webinars provides the benefits of short teaching sessions that do not require presenters and attendees to be together in a classroom: each webinar has a short duration (60-90 minutes) and can be conducted in part using a "Question&Answer" format (Q&A), which encourages audience participation. The indicative structure of the webinars consists of two phases: oral presentations from 1 or 2 invited/selected speakers from project partner institutions, eventually in the form of short interviews by a science journalist or WP9 staff (no longer than 45 minutes), followed by a Q&A session in order to collect feedback by interested stakeholders and the civil society (no longer than 1 hour). The webinars will be transmitted via streaming to allow a wider participation.

As for the contents of the online webinars, possible proposals of topics to be addressed are: FOSSR infrastructures and their potential; tools developed by FOSSR and how to use them; Knowledge Graphs; policy learning; FOSSR innovation in data collection and analysis. The final contents will be agreed with the project coordinator and WPs representatives.

The invited speakers, invited by the WP9 organizers in agreement with FOSSR coordinator, will have to make available their presentations for publication in the project website, nourishing the common repository of dissemination materials.

The suggested structures of the seminars/webinars are indicative and flexible, according to the invited speakers and the contents addressed, which will have to be established in synergy with the policy makers sessions described in the next paragraph and, possibly, also with the WP8 activities. Evaluation questionnaires will be prepared and submitted to the participants after each webinar/seminar to evaluate the appreciation level and possibly improve the effectiveness of the format. Moreover, in the case of the seminars, a discussant from the scientific community will be involved for the same aim.

Both the online seminars and webinars will be delivered through a zoom platform, in Italian language unless there are foreign participants; all the related written materials will be prepared in English to encourage the interest beyond the Italian national context. Our target is to reach a total of at least 100 participants distributed among the 6 events. Participants will have to fill in a registration form to let us monitor the reaching of our participation goals.

We expect to organize 2 seminars by the end of 2023, 1 seminar and 2 webinars in 2024, 1 webinar by April of 2025.

5.2 Policymakers sessions

FOSSR wants to exploit its existing contacts to policy makers starting from the contacts already developed within CESSDA ERIC, SHARE ERIC and RISIS as well as to explore new opportunities to gain influence on policy areas and specific policies relevant to the project's goals. FOSSR is committed toward establishing a deep networking with national regional policy makers such as Ministries and Departments of Education, as well as other relevant Public

Organizations potentially sensitive to the project aims. People involved will be engaged to jointly organize workshops and/or working sessions to present results and discuss their needs with a view of learning from these interactions about the future directions of FOSSR development to improve the possibility to produce social impact.

One mean devoted to pursuing the mentioned aims is the organization of policy makers sessions. The policy makers sessions are online participatory events (citizen science events) to foster the engagement of decision makers. They will be periodically organized to communicate the services of the thematic network, while outreaching about the potential of CESSDA ERIC, SHARE ERIC and RISIS in terms of informed decisions on economic and social change. This format is designed as an awareness event with a learning attitude: by demonstrating the novelty of the outputs and the type of use expected, decision makers can learn from the audience through their feedback, as well as observe how data, tools and services should improve the understanding of economic and social change. This kind of policy-oriented events aim at strengthening the ability of decision makers to interpret data and use them for policy design (ex-ante evaluation of the different options) and for ex post evaluation of policies and their impact.

The agenda is articulated based on the arguments that are also elaborated through Policy Briefs (See ANNEX 1) with the aim of demonstrating how project resources can produce social and political impact.

The policy maker sessions will be organized by the three RIs involved in FOSSR (at least one event per infrastructure). The structure of the sessions is generally articulated in three parts:

- the first in which main topics and evidence of the policy brief are presented and explored in depth (Introduction and questions, Topic addressed, How FOSSR can address, Policy evidence).
- the second in which one or two discussants (possibly policy makers involved in related topics) comment on the presentation.
- the third of open discussion on the issues raised. This part should be devoted to highlight new needs and critical issues related to the resources supplied by FOSSR.

Different structure of the events can be applied according to the type of demonstration proposed and the targeted audience involved. In this respect, comments and suggestions from the Stakeholders advisory board SAB will be considered.

The duration of the policy makers session should be 90-120 minutes; they will be carried out in different ways -online only, hybrid, physical meeting, with a preference for the participation in presence. The location will be distributed in different regions, balancing the events between regions in the south and in rest of Italy.

The planning for the project duration foresees at least 3 policy maker sessions and the drafting of 3 Policy Briefs, which shall involve 60 participants.

5.3 Networking

This task promotes and strengthens the networking between FOSSR and the other thematic networks of research infrastructures in Social and Cultural Innovation (H2IOSC, RESILIENCE.ITA). Furthermore, a networking will be envisaged with one thematic network led by CNR in the DIGIT area (Open.IT) to integrate developments of D4SCIENCE and

OpenAIRE Research Graph. Networking is also foreseen with universities that are Italian nodes of infrastructures thematically linked to FOSSR (GSS and GUIDE). This action will be carried out through 3 annual meetings (FOSSR kick off at M1, first FOSSR annual meeting at M12, second FOSSR annual meeting at M24) and exchanges of information during the dissemination activities.

6. OUTREACH AND OPEN TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS

6.1 Media Data Center (MDC)

The Media Data Center (MDC) is the system responsible for fostering open access to the data contained in the Open Cloud infrastructure. The MDC will offer a searchable and customizable engine for generating live, API-accessible feeds of metadata (RSS/JSON), content (RSS) and data (JSON) from data archives. For instance, the MDC may be configured to provide information about updates on specific topics or about the work of a person.

Human agents (i.e., users) will then be able to consult the catalogue of information provided by the MDC, choose the information that is of interest to them, and subscribe to receive updates when new content on those topics is published (e.g., when a new social science research article is published).

The MDC will also provide this information in machine-processable formats, to allow the development of software agents able to process the data and updates generated by the MDC (e.g., converting the data into a web page, drawing a chart, notifying a series of users via email, storing data in a database, etc.).

This will allow easy (even automated) data and content syndication, also in visual form, providing active support, e.g., to data journalism.

The architecture of the MDC is based on the W3C's Web of Things (WoT) standards, which provide a set of standardized technology building blocks that support application development by following the well-known and successful Web paradigm.

WoT introduces a simple interaction abstraction based on properties (i.e., read only values) and events (i.e., data streams).

All metadata, including the information needed to enable this common abstraction, is documented in what is called Thing Description (TD). The TD is at the base of the W3C Web of Things architecture and provides information on which data and functions are exposed, which protocol is used, how data is encoded and structured, and security mechanism is used to control access, and further machine-readable and human-readable metadata. TDs are expressed in JSON-LD and can be hosted in a repository such as a TD Directory, which represents a catalogue of the functionalities and information offered by the system.

This approach ensures flexibility and interoperability and enables the reuse of established standards and tools.

The work for this task will start at month 6 and will last 25 months. Agile frameworks and methodologies will be applied to develop the prototype, allowing to make the solution usable

from the early stages of the implementation process, and to facilitate the execution of tests and feed a feedback chain. The executive phase will therefore be split into iterations (sprints) consistent with the design phase.

6.2 ZENODO Community space

FOSSR-Zenodo community space is used as repository of FOSSR research outcomes. It is directly embedded in OpenAIRE and has efficient search functionalities enabling to browse and download specific document types, such as training materials, conference presentations, policy briefs, publications, and to search for them in relation to different FOSSR focuses.

Zenodo fulfils two main purposes:

- 1) Repository for FOSSR activities and research outcomes from partners in the FOSSR project, such as documentations of data/service/tools developments, training materials, but also conference presentations and working papers, media, etc.
- 2) Repository for research outcomes from FOSSR users, e.g., in the form of conference presentations, working papers, publications, new datasets, visualizations, etc. Note that this is a main principle of Access in relation to FOSSR inscription to Open Science.

Following the FOSSR Code of Conduct, all users shall upload their outcomes in that space.

Communication team will improve through different direct and indirect tools and channels the awareness of partners, users, and stakeholders on this resource.

7. GENERAL PLANNING OF ACTIVITIES

Table 2 – Planning of activities

<i>WHAT (milestone)</i>	<i>ABOUT (indicators)</i>	<i>WHEN (bimester deadline)</i>
Setting of the format for the Online seminars and Webinars	Planning of the online seminars and webinars	1 (done)
Kick off FOSSR	Kick off FOSSR	1 (done)
Design of the FOSSR website structure	Creation of the structure of the website	1 (done)
Setting of the format for Online policy makers' sessions and Policy Briefs	Planning Online policy makers' sessions and Policy Briefs	1 (done)
Opening of the website	Website is online. Structure of the monitoring of the website indicators.	2
Opening of the FOSSR social media pages (FB, Twitter, Youtube, LinkedIn)	Social media pages (FB, Twitter, Youtube, LinkedIn) are online. Setting of the engagement indicators and dissemination chart.	2
First FOSSR annual meeting	Organization of FOSSR annual meeting	6
1 Online policy makers' sessions and 1 Policy Briefs delivered	1 Online policy makers' sessions and 1 Policy Briefs delivered.	9
First 3 Online seminars/Webinars delivered	3 Online seminars/Webinars delivered	9
Promotion of Open Access and Transnational Access 1	Media Data Center is online; open access publications and accesses (virtual or physical).	9
Second FOSSR annual meeting	Organization of the second FOSSR annual meeting	12
2 Online policy makers' sessions and 2 Policy Briefs delivered	2 Online policy makers' sessions and 2 Policy Briefs delivered.	15
Second 3 Online seminars/Webinars delivered	3 Online seminars/Webinars delivered	15
Promotion of Open Access and Transnational Access 2	open access publications and accesses (virtual or physical).	15

Table 2 – Reporting planning

<i>Deliverables</i>	<i>When (deadline)</i>
D9.1 Communication and dissemination plan	M3 (done)
D9.2 Release of the FOSSR website	M6
D9.4 First report on communication, dissemination and outreach	M18
D9.5 Release of Media Data Center	M18
D9.7 Report on networking activities and results	
D9.6 Second report on communication, dissemination and outreach	M30
D9.8 Report on transnational access	M30

8. IMPACT AND MONITORING

Long-term achievements for all the RIs involved that can derive from this integrated effort, are:

- i) A systemic improvement of the volume and quality of research in the social sciences, matching the increasingly demanding standards defined by the top scientific journals and associations.
- ii) Expanding and upgrading the methodological approaches of the national social science research community.
- iii) Providing reliable data and expertise to decision-makers aimed at the development of evidence-based solutions to social issues.

More precisely, FOSSR wants to generate a significant scientific impact in the broad field of social sciences, and social impact in communities of non-academic users that can improve the robustness of the evidence as a fundament of decision making.

The quality of the outcome and the actions toward promoting high level training and public awareness shall increase the number of scholars and early career researchers, especially those in the South of Italy, which improve their knowledge and therefore develops different uses of the innovative methods and instruments for data collection and for data analysis provided by FOSSR. Scholars will access the online FOSSR resources under a completely open conditions for research purposes; users are also supposed to integrate the data available in the Open Cloud Platform with data and analysis developed, thus improving practices and culture about the value of the open circulation of knowledge.

FOSSR will establish access rules based on the principles already applied by the infrastructures involved that allow open use of data for any scientific research activity, accepting the project's code of conduct (conditional open access).

One further item to be mentioned is the attention toward gender equality. Therefore, FOSSR will bring a special attention to encourage the involvement of women in the training activities and in the governance of the project, generating an impact in terms of having a good gender balance in the users that FOSSR will be able to attract. A Gender Equality Plan (GEP) is developed within the WP2 as point of reference for the FOSSR activities.

As to the societal impact, FOSSR resources shall capture the attention of policy makers to use the resources for specific investigations about major emerging scientific and political issues such as: declining fertility; work-family arrangements in a context of changing work conditions; access to and accumulation of economic resources; technology use and risk behaviours among young people; intergenerational solidarity and long-term care needs in old age, career and internationalization of highly skilled human resources.

Many of the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) to measure impact go through these main expected impacts, beyond the interactions with users about conditions of use and future developments:

1. promoting scientific excellence
2. increasing the attractiveness of scientific activities
3. attracting new researchers from other territories

4. diversifying the catchment area
5. increasing the positioning of the scientific community
6. promoting Open Science practices

There are two channels through which we can foster the innovation role of the FOSSR thematic network: differentiate the supply of training, communication, and dissemination in order to address the different needs of our stakeholders and increase the channels through which FOSSR can impact them.

Potential Impacts are thus associated with the efforts to disseminate results obtained using tools and services. To ensure impact specific measures will be developed supporting wide communication and outreach of these results, through the production of policy briefs and through the extensive use of media actions. This will be complemented by targeted interactions with researchers and policy makers engaging with them through awareness events to present results and discuss their needs as to new methodologies and exploitation of services.

Furthermore, researchers dealing with different research topics in social sciences and with different disciplinary background have specific needs that FOSSR tools and services can meet. Researchers play an important role in the circulation of results and tailoring to the policy issues of the stakeholders that employ them. This is an important audience to be engaged deeply in the FOSSR activities. The Media Data Centre fosters the automatic interaction with data by providing data and content syndication.

As to the scientific impact, we expect to develop innovative and unique solutions for data collection and data analysis, as well as innovative way to access data and services. The quality of the outcome and the actions toward promoting high level training and public awareness shall increase the number of scholars and early career researchers, especially those in the South of Italy, which improve their knowledge and therefore develops different uses of the innovative methods and instruments for data collection and for data analysis provided by FOSSR. Scholars will access the online FOSSR resources under a completely open conditions for research purposes; users are also supposed to integrate the data available in the Open Cloud Platform with data and analysis developed, thus improving practices and culture about the value of the open circulation of knowledge. In this respect, we also foreseen to attract scholars from abroad, especially young scholars, which might represent at least 5% of the transnational access foreseen by the program and could provide a push toward a further internationalization of the Italian universities. Therefore, we will bring a special attention to encourage the involvement of women in the training activities and in the governance of the project; we expect to generate an impact in terms of having a good gender balance in the users that FOSSR will be able to attract. In this respect the Gender Equality Plan shall help to monitor the situation suggesting measures to increase the women involved.

As to the societal impact, we expect FOSSR resources shall capture the attention of policy makers to use the resources for specific investigations about major emerging scientific and political issues such as: declining fertility; work-family arrangements in a context of changing work conditions; access to and accumulation of economic resources; technology use and risk behaviours among young people; intergenerational solidarity and long-term care needs in old age, career and internationalization of highly skilled human resources. Also, items related with the local competitiveness, the innovation processes, and firms' characteristics at local level, can capture the interest of policy makers. This attention can bring to use of the FOSSR resources under contracts coming from national, international, and regional competitive call, which can

guarantee the sustainability of the thematic network beyond the end of the project. Finally, we expect that the network of services and data could become a resource for longitudinal analyses on key issues linked to the realization of sustainable development goals such as health and innovation.

The feasibility of the expected impact shall be guaranteed by the creation at the end of the project of a Joint Research Unit (JRU), joining together CNR, the universities that are part of the Italian node of CESSDA, SHARE and RISIS, and ISTAT. The JRU is supposed to provide a strong institutional framework for participating in open calls and to inscribe the FOSSR activities in the SISTAN network. The possibility of enlarging the partners to other universities and research organizations which can contribute to the thematic network aims and goals will be considered.

8.1 Key Performance Indicators

Communication Team monitor periodically users' views and needs through on-line feedbacks after activities developed (access, workshops, conferences special sessions, communication events). The team develops some activities indicators based on results achieved with respect to the planned target to check whether there are problems with the program implementation.

Table 3 – Activities Indicators

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Target M18</i>	<i>Target M30</i>
Policy makers' sessions and participants	1 (15)	2(30)
Policy Briefs downloads	30	60
Online seminars/Webinars delivered and participants	3 (50)	6 (100)
Open access publications	5	10
Accesses (virtual or physical)	10	20

Also, key engagement indicators are collected to illustrate where we are with the support of robust evidence.

Table 4 – Key Performance/Engagement Indicators

<i>Tool</i>	<i>Indicator</i>
Users awareness	N. requests for access
	N. master and PhD students using the RI
	N. people not involved RI communities
Events	N. events organized
	N. participants at events
	N. papers presented at Conferences
Publications and materials	N. papers published
	N. presentations at events
	N. materials distributed at events
	N. materials uploaded in Zenodo
Outreach to the public	N. materials downloaded in Zenodo
	N. presentations to stakeholders
	N. presentations to policy makers
	N. contacts of mailing lists
	N. contacts by direct contact

	N. contacts through mailing campaign
	N. contacts through web and social media
Website	N. visits
	N. unique visitors
	N. Newsletters downloaded or viewed
	N. videos visualizations
	N. documents uploaded
	N. documents downloaded
	N. policy brief downloaded
	N. click on social media link
Social Media	N. tweets sent
	N. like on Twitter
	Total number of followers on Twitter
	N. shared posts on Facebook
	N. like on Facebook page
	N. YouTube videos uploaded
	N. YouTube videos visualized
Media relations	N. press releases, memos published on FOSSR
	N. articles, forewords and interviews written on FOSSR
Audio-visual production	N. video and storytelling published
	N. pictures published
	N. event cards published
Internal communication	N. visits to workspace
	N. updates, news, events, shared on workspace

CONCLUSIONS

The deliverable presents the medium- and long-term planning of dissemination and communication activities, main priorities and actions devoted to promote visibility, to engage potential users and stakeholders, and to build a large and active community around FOSSR facilities.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	Description
BOCCONI	Università degli studi di Milano Bocconi
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CID ETHIC	Centro Interdipartimentale per l'Etica e l'Integrità nella Ricerca
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
CRUI	Conferenza dei Rettori delle Università italiane
DSU	Dipartimento Scienze Umane e Sociali, Patrimonio Culturale
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GSS	Generations & Gender Survey
GUIDE	Growing Up In Digital Europe
ICAR	Istituto di Calcolo e Reti ad Alte Prestazioni
INAPP	Istituto nazionale per l'analisi delle politiche pubbliche
ISTC	Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie della Cognizione,
ISTI	Istituto di Scienza e Tecnologie dell'Informazione "Alessandro Faedo"
H2IOSC	Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud
JRU	Joint research units
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KOM	Kick-off Meeting
KPI	Key performance indicators
LUISS	Libera università internazionale degli studi sociali Guido Carli
MDC	Media Data Center
MEF	Ministero dell'Economia e delle Finanze
MISE	Ministero delle Imprese e del Made in Italy
MUR	Ministero dell'università e della ricerca
NGO	Non Governmental Organization
NRRP	The National Recovery and Resilience Plan
PhD	Doctor of Philosophy
RIs	Research Infrastructure
RISIS	Research infrastructure for research and innovation policy studies
RSS	Really Simple Syndication
SS	Social Sciences
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SAB	Stakeholders advisory board
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe
SISTAN	Sistema Statistico Nazionale
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
UNIBO	Università degli Studi di Bologna
UNICATT	Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore
UNIMI	Università degli Studi di Milano
UNISI	Università di Siena
UVR	Unità Valorizzazione della Ricerca
WoT	Web of Thing
WP	Work Package

ANNEX 1 POLICY BRIEF FORMAT

MISSIONE 4
ISTRUZIONE
RICERCA

FOSSR
Fostering Open Science in Social Science Research
Innovative tools and services to investigate economic and societal change

TITLE
SUBTITLE

FOSSR Policy Brief Series

Issue # | Month and year

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero
dell'Università
e della Ricerca

Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE
DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

Consiglio Nazionale
della Ricerca

OUTLINE

- 1 Introduction and questions
- 2 Topic addressed
- 3 How FOSSR can address
- 4 Policy evidence

Presentation

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1. Introduction and questions

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2. Topic addressed

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3. How FOSSR can address

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4. Policy evidence

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FOSSR - Fostering Open Science in Social Science Research aims to become an Italian Open Science Cloud, along the lines of the European Open Science Cloud project, in which to integrate innovative services developed by the project for data collection, data curation and Fairness, and data analysis on economic and societal change. FOSSR fosters the building of an integrated knowledge sharing platform, a single point of access to all the tools and services made available by the Italian nodes of social science infrastructures: CESSDA, SHARE and RISIS adopt the common theme of the development of Open Science in the Italian context with the goal of creating a framework of tools and services for the social science scholar community.

FOSSR wants to promote toward multiple audiences, a widespread knowledge and awareness of the data and methodologies employed in empirical social science, fostering the growth of a broad societal environment favourable to further thriving of social science research in Italy, providing easy, open, streamlined access to social science data through innovative interfaces. The integration of this pool of resources shall concretely contribute to the realization of open science for scholars in social sciences, going with an important program of scientific training on methods and instruments for social science research based on FAIR empirical data.

FOSSR Policy Brief Series aim to communicate key findings from the FOSSR thematic network to a non-specialized audience with a strong emphasis on the demonstration of usage cases of FOSSR resources. The series can accomplish two goals: improving the use of data for evidence-based policymaking and assisting the stakeholders in making informed decisions.

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